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Antioxidative and cytotoxic activity of essential oils and extracts of *Satureja montana* L., *Coriandrum sativum* L. and *Ocimum basilicum* L. obtained by supercritical fluid extraction

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Graphical abstract

Antioxidative and cytotoxic activity of essential oils and extracts of *Satureja montana* L., *Coriandrum sativum* L. and *Ocimum basilicum* L. obtained by supercritical fluid extraction

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Highlights

- Investigation of SFE of *S. montana*, *C. sativum*, *O. basilicum* and herbal mixture.
- Chemical profile of herbal mixture and pure plants extracts was completely different.
- High antioxidant activity of obtained CO₂ extracts and isolated essential oils.
- Essential oil and extracts of *S. montana* exhibited high cytotoxicity.
- Chemometric approach in correlation of terpenoids and biological activity.

Abstract

In this study, lipid extracts obtained by supercritical fluid extraction and essential oils of *Satureja montana* L., *Coriandrum sativum* L. and *Ocimum basilicum* L., as well as the mixture of these

aromatic herbs were investigated. Obtained extracts and essential oils were analyzed by GC-MS and GC-FID. The chemical profile of obtained EOs and extracts showed that carvacrol was the major compound in *S. montana*, while in *C. sativum* and *O. basilicum* linalool was the most abundant compound. In the EO obtained from herbal mixture of three aromatic plants, the predominant compounds were linalool and carvacrol, followed by geraniol, γ -terpinene and eugenol, similar with extract obtained by SFE (100 bar, 40°C). The antioxidant activity was determined by DPPH assay, while antiproliferative activity of the obtained CO₂ extracts and the essential oils were evaluated *in vitro* against three different human cancer cell lines (HeLa, MDA-MB-453, K562) and normal MRC-5 human fibroblasts.

Keywords: Medicinal plants; supercritical fluid extraction; essential oil; chemical profile; antioxidant and antiproliferative activity.

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1. Introduction

The *Lamiaceae* and *Apiaceae* species could be considered as the richest in medicinal plants, with wide range in biological activity, and a wide diversity in phytochemicals. From ancient times, they have been used in folk medicine and to improve the flavor of different types of foods. Moreover, the use of aromatic plants and spices in phytotherapy is mostly attributed to different activities of their essential oils (EOs), such as antimicrobial, antiinflammatory, antioxidative, antiproliferative/anticancer, antiviral and hepatoprotective activities [1,2].

Great attention, among aromatic plants, is related to *Satureja montana* L. (winter savory), *Coriandrum sativum* L. (coriander) and *Ocimum basilicum* L. (sweet basil), which are widely distributed and cultivated in Mediterranean countries. As important medicinal plants in traditional medicine, these aromatic herbs are usually used as spices in culinary.

Satureja montana is an evergreen perennial shrub with papery flavor. The whole plant, the EO and extracts are used in the traditional medicine for their medicinal benefits especially upon the whole digestive system. *S. montana* contains various biologically active constituents such as EOs, tannins, triterpenes and flavonoids [3]. Diuretic effects of *S. montana* is attributed to the major phenolic compounds of essential oil, thymol and carvacrol [4]. Its extracts possess antiinflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidative, antiproliferative properties [5] and an important anti-HIV-1 activity [6]. *Coriandrum sativum* belongs to *Apiaceae* family, cultivated mostly for seeds, which have a lemony citrus flavor. Coriander seeds are used as condiment in liqueurs, teas, meat products and pickles [7]. In traditional medicine they have been used for gastrointestinal problems. Moreover, coriander seeds are a good source of polyphenols, particularly phenolic acids and flavonoids [8]. Essential oil (rich in linalool) and various extracts of *C. sativum* expressed antimicrobial [9], anticarcinogenic [10], antioxidant [11] and antidiabetic activities [12]. *Ocimum basilicum* is popular culinary aromatic herb, with fresh, minty and sweet flavor. Traditionally, it has been used as a medicinal plant in the treatment of headaches, respiratory and urinary infections [13]. Basil is a rich source of EO, phenolic compounds and flavonoids. Basil's EO contains linalool, methyl-chavicol (estragol), followed by methyl-eugenol and methyl-cinnamate, as the most common compounds. Different extracts, rich in polyphenolic compounds, and EO have been shown antiviral [14], antioxidant [15], antidiabetic activities [16] and inhibitory activity against HIV-1 [17].

All this EOs and extracts have appreciable pharmacological effects, so using mixture of those three herbs to achieve greater therapeutic efficacy is of interest. Research of antioxidant activity of essential oil from a hepatoprotective herbal mix [18] and extracts obtained by SFE from herbal mix (tulsi, bay and cardamom) [19], indicated better bioactivity of combined extracts of plants over individual plants/extracts.

Essential oils, from aromatic plants are generally extracted by hydrodistillation (HD). These classical extraction methods of volatile constituents/essential oils have several problems due to the thermal degradation, oxidation and hydrolysis of some compounds of the EOs. Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) with CO₂ can be employed as novel extraction technique where mentioned limitations can be overcome. Carbon dioxide is non-toxic, cheap, non-inflammable and “green” solvent, easy removable from the product, with the moderate critical temperature and pressure (T_c = 31.1°C, P_c = 73.8 bar), which allows to operate at mild conditions. Moreover, this process allows a continuous enhancement of the solvent power/selectivity by manipulation of process parameters (pressure and temperature) of supercritical fluid, resulting in different extract compositions [20].

These characteristics of SFE, lead to isolation of various bioactive compounds, such as antioxidants, tocopherols, carotenoids, unsaturated fatty acids, etc. These compounds can play an important role in food technology and human health, in prevention some of the modern diseases.

The main objectives of present work were to investigate the composition of essential oils and supercritical fluid extracts of *Satureja montana* L., *Coriandrum sativum* L. and *Ocimum basilicum* L., as well as mixture of these tree herbs. Supercritical extraction process has been applied regarding its efficiency for extraction of temperature unstable volatile compounds. The combination of these three aromatic herbs (*S. montana*, *C. sativum* and *O. basilicum*) was with idea to obtain extracts and essential oils richest in bioactive compounds (with different chemical profile as individual investigated plant), and to estimate their potential synergistic interaction. Another goal of this study, was to evaluate antioxidant properties of obtained essential oils and extracts, as well as antiproliferative activity *in vitro* against three human cancer cell lines: the human cervix adenocarcinoma HeLa cells, human chronic myelogenous leukemia K562 cells, breast cancer MDA-MB-453 cells and normal fibroblast MRC-5 cells. Regarding the previous information, these medicinal plants and its extracts are considered to have a significant importance in pharmacy and medicine.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Commercial carbon dioxide (Messer, Novi Sad, Serbia) purity >99.98% was used for laboratory supercritical fluid extraction. The standard compounds for GC analysis (GC purity) were purchased by Ehrenstorfen, Germany and Carl Roth, Germany, 1,1-Diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl-hydrate (DPPH) was purchased from Sigma (Sigma-Aldrich GmbH, Steinheim, Germany). MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) was produced by Sigma Chemicals Co. All other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade.

2.2. Plant material

The investigated plant materials (coriander seed, basil leaves and flowering tops and winter savory herb) were cultivated at the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Novi Sad, Alternative Crops Department, Bački Petrovac, Serbia, in 2013. The collected plant materials were air dried and stored at room temperature. The dried plant material was grounded in a domestic blender and the particle size of material was determined using sieve sets (CISA, Cedaceria Industrial, Spain). Moisture content of plant material was analyzed using standard procedure, i.e., by drying the plant sample at 105°C until constant weight. This analysis was performed in three replicates. Moisture content and mean particle size (d_p) are presented in Table 1.

These three aromatic plants were mixed in the same mass ratio (1:1:1) representing a sample marked as CBS, which was investigated in the same manner. Its moisture content and mean particle size are presented in Table 1.

2.3. Hydrodistillation

The content of essential oil in investigated plants was determined by hydrodistillation according to the standard *Ph. Jug.* IV procedure [21].

2.4. Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction

The extraction process was carried out on laboratory scale high pressure extraction plant (HPEP, NOVA, Swiss, Efferikon, Switzerland) [22]. The main plant parts and properties, by manufacturer specification were: gas cylinder with CO₂, the diaphragm type compressor with pressure range up to 1000 bar, extractor with heating jacket for heating medium with internal volume 200 mL, maximum operating pressure of 700 bar, separator with heating jacket for heating medium (with internal volume 200 mL, maximum operating pressure of 250 bar), pressure control valve, temperature regulation system and regulation valves.

The ground sample of each herb and herbal mixture (50.0 g) were placed in an extractor vessel. The extraction process was carried out and extraction yield was measured after 30, 60, 90, 120, 180 and 240 min of extraction, in order to study the dynamics of the separation process. Investigated values of pressure were 100 and 300 bar at the temperature of 40°C. A flow rate of carbon dioxide, expressed under normal conditions, was 0.2 kg CO₂/h. The separator conditions were 15 bar and 25°C. After each extraction, obtained extract was placed in glass bottle, sealed and stored at 4°C to prevent any possible degradation.

2.5. Chromatographic procedure

GC–MS and GC-FID analysis were performed on Agilent GC6890N system according to previously described procedure [23]. In the case of GC–MS analysis, gas chromatograph was coupled with Agilent MS5759 mass spectrometer. The HP-5MS column (30 m length, 0.25 mm inner diameter with 0.25 mm film thickness) was used. Helium flow rate was 2 mL/min, while temperature was as follows: injector 250°C, detector 300°C, initial 60°C with linear increase of 4°C/min to 150°C. Samples were dissolved in methylene chloride, while injected volume of those solutions was 5 µL with split ratio of 30:1. Compounds were identified by comparing obtained spectral data to those one from NIST 05 and Wiley 7n mass spectral libraries and with spectral data of analytical standards. GC-FID analysis was employed for quantitative analysis of compounds in analyzed samples. Standard solutions were prepared dissolving standard compounds in methylene chloride in concentration range of 1–500 µg/mL. Standard solutions were used to create calibration curve, which described the dependence of peak area on concentration of standard compounds ($R^2 > 0.99$). Obtained results were expressed as mg of compound per g of extract (mg/g E). All experiments were performed in triplicate and results are given as mean values

2.6. Antioxidant assay - DPPH test

The free radical scavenging activity of lipid extracts and EOs was determined using simple and fast spectrophotometric method as described by Espin et al. [24]. Briefly, prepared extracts dissolved in ethyl acetate were mixed with methanol (96%) and 90 µM 2,2-diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH) to give different final concentrations. After incubation for 60 min at room temperature, the absorbance

of samples was measured at 515 nm. Radical scavenging capacity (%RSC) was calculated by following equation:

$$\%RSC = 100 - (A_{sample} \times 100) / A_{blank} \quad (1)$$

where A_{sample} is the absorbance of sample solution and A_{blank} is the absorbance of control. Antioxidant activity was also expressed as IC_{50} which represent the concentration of test (extract solution) required for obtaining the 50% of radical scavenging capacity, expressed as μg per mL. All experiments were prepared in triplicate, and results are expressed as mean values \pm standard deviation.

2.7. Cell lines - treatment

HeLa, MDA-MB-453, K562 and MRC-5 cell lines were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (Manassas, VA, USA). All cell lines were maintained in the recommended RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated (56°C) fetal bovine serum (FBS), l-glutamine (3 mmol/L), streptomycin (100 mg/mL), penicillin (100 IU/mL), and 25 mM HEPES and adjusted to pH 7.2 by bicarbonate solution. Cells were grown in a humidified atmosphere of 95% air and 5% CO_2 at 37°C. Stock solutions (200 mg/mL) of compounds, were prepared in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), and diluted in complete nutrient RPMI-1640 medium to the required working concentrations. HeLa cells (2000 cells per well), MDA-MB-453 cells (3000 cells per well), and MRC-5 cells (5000 cells per well) were seeded into 96-well microtiter plates, and 20 h later, after the cell adherence, five different concentrations of investigated EOs and extracts were added to the wells. Final concentrations applied to target cells were in the range of 0.0625 to 1 mg/mL, except to the control wells, where only nutrient medium was added to the cells. K562 cells (5000 cells per well) were seeded, 2 h before addition of investigated EOs and extracts to give the desired final concentrations. The cultures were incubated for 72 h at 37°C.

2.8. Determination of cell survival (MTT test)

The effect of EOs and CO_2 extracts on cancer cell survival was determined by MTT test (microculture tetrazolium test), according to the methodology described by Mosmann [25] with modification by Ohno and Abe [26], 72 h upon addition of the compounds.

Briefly, 20 μL of MTT solution (5 mg/mL in PBS) were added to each well. Samples were incubated for further 4 h at 37°C in 5% CO_2 and humidified air atmosphere. Then, 100 μL of 10% SDS were added to solubilize the insoluble formazan formed from the conversion of the MTT dye by viable cells. The number of viable cells in each well was proportional to the intensity of the absorbance of light, which was then read in an ELISA plate reader at 570 nm. Absorbance (A) at 570 nm was measured 24 h later. The cell survival (%), was calculated according to the formula: Absorbance of a sample with cells grown in the presence of various concentrations of the investigated essential oils and extracts /absorbance of cell control \times 100. It was implied that A of the blank was always subtracted from A of the corresponding sample with target cells. IC_{50} concentration was defined as the concentration of an agent inhibiting cell survival by 50%, compared with a vehicle-treated control. Untreated cells were used as positive control. All experiments were done in triplicate.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Essential oil characterization

The raw material characterization and content of EOs from *S. montana*, *C. sativum*, *O. basilicum* and mixture of these three herbs (CBS) are presented in Table 1. Using standard

hydrodistillation process, the content of EO of herbal mixture (CBS) was 0.78% (v/w). The content of EOs from *S. montana*, *C. sativum*, *O. basilicum* were 1.15, 0.75 and 0.67% (v/w), respectively, and are in accordance with previously reported research [27-29]. It can be mention that EO yield depends of several factors: seasonal, geographical and climate variation, generative stage, level of macro and micronutrients in soil and drying conditions to which the plant material is exposed.

The EO compounds were qualitative and quantitative determined by two chromatographic methods, GC–MS and GC–FID. In the Table 2 are presented the results of quantitative analysis. The predominant compound in *S. montana* EO was carvacrol with 571.00 mg/g extract (E), followed by γ -terpinene (52.20 mg/g E). In the EOs of *C. sativum* and *O. basilicum* the major compound was linalool with the content of 782.00 mg/g E and 772.00 mg/g E, respectively.

Essential oil of *O. basilicum* also contains eugenol (39.60 mg/g E), eucalyptol (1,8-cineole) (32.10 mg/g E), geraniol (22.00 mg/g E) and methyl-chavicol (21.00 mg/g E) as following compounds. In the EO obtained from herbal mixture of three aromatic plants (CBS sample), the predominant compounds were linalool (422.00 mg/g E) and carvacrol (172.00 mg/g E), followed by geraniol (29.00 mg/g E), γ -terpinene (18.60 mg/g E) and eugenol (15.30 mg/g E). On the other hand, the GC-MS analysis of EO from herbal mixture showed completely different chemical profile (70.36% identified components) than that EOs obtained from individual plants. Few compounds (such as α -pinene, β -pinene and d-limonene) showed a higher content in herbal mixture (CBS) EO than in obtained EOs from investigated plants.

Chemical profile of *S. montana* EO, rich in carvacrol, has been shown that this cultivated species belongs to carvacrol chemotype (chemotype A), like others species in Mediterranean region [30]. However, literature review showed variation between chemical compositions, depending of geographical location and stages of plant development [31]. Generally, *S. montana* EOs were characterized by high percentage of the monoterpene phenols, carvacrol and/or thymol, two isomeric compounds with different position of hydroxyl group on their phenol ring, with very close biosynthetic relationship with their precursors (γ -terpinene and *p*-cymene). Essential oil of *O. basilicum*, with linalool as the major compound, clearly indicates that the plant belongs to chemotype A (European chemotype) [32].

3.2. Supercritical fluid extraction and characterization of extracts

Supercritical fluid extraction was performed at temperature of 40°C and two different pressures 100 bar and 300 bar, in order to extract first EO and the second total extracts. The effect of pressure at constant temperature on the extraction process expressed as extraction yield (mass (g) of obtained extract per 100 g of dry plant material) of investigated plants and herbal mixture is shown in Figure 1. The kinetic curves shows two standard extraction periods, the first initial, rapid extraction where the easy accessible solute is dissolved by the supercritical (SC) CO₂, and the second - slow extraction period, which is diffusion controlled. The fast extraction period was expressed during the first 2 hours, after which obtained amount of extracts were lower. Additionally, the increase of pressure (from 100 to 300 bar at constant temperature) enhances the kinetics and greatly reduces the extraction time and significantly increases the extraction efficiency (higher extraction yield).

Extraction yield at 100 bar and 40°C varied from 1.5 to 2.0 %, while at 300 bar and 40°C it was in range from 2.07 to 5.60 % (Table 1). Increasing in pressure from 100 to 300 bar at constant temperature (40°C), i.e. increase in CO₂ density (from 0.628 to 0.909 kg/m³), caused a 2 or 3 times greater extraction yield. As pressure increase, the dissolving ability of CO₂ increase, causing better

solubility of high-molecular weight compounds in plant matrix, which are co-extracted with EO compounds, and resulting in higher amount of extract.

Extraction yield of *S. montana* obtained by SC – CO₂ at 100 bar and 40°C was 1.50%, and at 300 bar and 40°C was 4.02%. A similar observation was noticed by Grosso et al. [27] at 100 bar and 40°C (1.8%). In our previous study, reported by Vladić et al. [33], extraction yield at 100 and 300 bar and 40°C (mean particle size 0.301 mm, flow rate 0.194 kg/h and extraction time of 4.5 h) were 1.88 and 2.95%, respectively. The difference in obtained extraction yield, in our and previous study, can be explained by using plant material cultivated in two different years. Extraction yield at 100 bar and 40°C obtained from *C. sativum* was 1.74%, and at 300 bar and 40°C it was 5.60%. Similar results were achieved by Pavlić et al. [34] at 100 bar and 40°C (1.52%), but some higher at 300 bar and 40°C (8.88%). According to Yepez et al. [35] extraction yield was 1.43% under the operation conditions of 115.5 bar and 311 K. SFE of *O. basilicum* at 100 and 300 bar yielded in 1.56 and 2.07%, respectively. Lachowicz et al. [36] reported that during 2 h of extraction at 103.3 bar and 40°C extraction yield was 0.51% and at 310 bar and 40°C it was 0.97%. According to Zeković et al. [37], under the operation conditions of 100 – 300 bar and 40°C extraction yields were in the range of 0.72 to 1.29%, lower than obtained in this study, but SFE was conducted with higher mean particle size of plant material ($d_p=0.65$ mm).

SFE of herbal mixture (CBS) at 100 bar and 40°C yielded 2.00% of extract. It was the highest obtained yield at that condition, and about 25% higher than that obtained from the individual plants. Extraction yield at 300 bar and 40°C was 4.29%, lower than extract obtained from the *C. sativum*, but higher than obtained from *S. montana* and *O. basilicum* at the same extraction condition. The difference in obtained extraction yield among herbal mixture and pure plants can be explained by influence of one of herb in mixture (possible *C. sativum*).

The results of chemical analyses of the obtained CO₂ extracts accomplished by GC–MS and GC–FID are presented in Table 2. Twelve components were detected and identified in extracts of *S. montana*, *C. sativum*, *O. basilicum* and herbal mixture (CBS), obtained by SFE. The percentage of total identified compounds decrease from 100 to 300 bar at the constant temperature. Three groups of volatile aromatic compounds were detected in analyzed extracts: monoterpene hydrocarbons, oxygenated monoterpenes and aromatic oxygenated monoterpenes. In EO and extracts of *S. montana* the most abundance group is aromatic oxygenated monoterpenes, while in *C. sativum* and *O. basilicum* EO and extracts dominant group is oxygenated monoterpenes (see Figure 2). The herbal mixture (CBS sample) EO, as dominant group has oxygenated monoterpenes (68%) followed by aromatic oxygenated monoterpenes (28%). CBS extract at 100 bar and 40°C has different ratio of monoterpene groups, where aromatic oxygenated monoterpenes (55%) was dominant, followed by oxygenated monoterpenes (33.4%).

The predominant compound in *S. montana* CO₂ extracts was carvacrol with 529.70 mg/g E (100 bar, 40°C) and 601.70 mg/g E (300 bar, 40°C). The main component in CO₂ extracts of *C. sativum* and *O. basilicum* was linalool. Its range from 456.00 mg/g E (100 bar, 40°C) to 291.20 mg/g E (300 bar, 40°C) in *C. sativum* extracts, while in *O. basilicum* extracts range from 301.00 mg/g E (100 bar, 40°C) to 379.00 mg/g E (300 bar, 40°C). Chemical profile of herbal mixture (CBS sample) CO₂ extract (52.20% identified components on 100 bar, 40°C) was completely different than that of extracts obtained from individual plants. The most abundant components in the CBS CO₂ extract were carvacrol (281.00 mg/g E), linalool (101.00 mg/g E), geraniol (61.00 mg/g E), γ -terpinene (42.00 mg/g E) and d-limonene (10.40 mg/g E) obtained at 100 bar and 40°C. Furthermore, increasing in pressure from 100 to 300 bar, reduce the amount of obtained compounds, except in the case of carvacrol which keep the same content. The lower content of linalool in *C. sativum* extract was observed at 300 bar and 40°C, then that at 100 bar

and 40°C. This is probably due to better solubility of monoterpenes in low CO₂ density [20]. On the other hand, the higher content of carvacrol (*S. montana* and CBS), linalool (*O. basilicum*), camphor (*O. basilicum*) and α -terpineol (*O. basilicum*) were obtained in the extracts achieved with CO₂ at 300 bar and 40°C. Different content of the same compound in obtained extracts can be explained by its different solubility in extraction solvent (carbon dioxide at different pressure and temperature) [38]. Besides, Zeković et al. [39] in previous SFE investigation of *C. sativum* demonstrated that chemical composition of obtained extracts depends on the solubility of certain component in SC-CO₂, and are in relationship with chemical structure.

A comparison of the chemical composition of the obtained CO₂ extracts (100 bar, 40°C) and that of the EOs revealed significant differences. The lower content of linalool was determined at lower pressure (100 bar, 40°C) in extracts from *C. sativum*, *O. basilicum* and CBS (four times lower), than that in EOs. In the CBS extracts (obtained at lower pressure) vs. EO, the content of carvacrol (281.00 mg/g E vs. 172.00 mg/g E), geraniol (61.00 mg/g E vs. 29.00 mg/g E) and γ -terpinene (42.00 mg/g E vs. 18.60 mg/g E) were approximately 2 times higher. Additional, a significant difference in the d-limonene content in the extract (10.40 mg/g E) and EO (3.70 mg/g E) was also observed.

3.3. Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity of obtained CO₂ extracts and isolated EOs was tested using DPPH spectrophotometric method. Assessed samples were able to reduce the stable violet DPPH radical to yellow DPPH-H, reaching 50% of reduction with IC₅₀ values ranging from 5.05 μ g/mL to 6.780 μ g/mL (Table 3). The highest antioxidant activity showed *S. montana* and *O. basilicum* EOs with IC₅₀ values of 5.05 μ g/mL and 6.94 μ g/mL, respectively. The antioxidant activity of CBS EO was approximately 6 times lower than antioxidant activity of *S. montana* EO, but very similar with extracts of *S. montana* obtained by supercritical extraction procedure (40°C, 100 and 300 bar). On the other hand, IC₅₀ values of CBS and *O. basilicum* extracts are very similar at lower and at higher pressures.

Antioxidant activity of *S. montana* EO found in this study is higher than reported by Čavar et al. [31] for Croatia origin, Serrano et al. [30] for Portugal origin, Miladi et al. [40] for France origin and Trifan et al. [41] for Romanian origin (see Table 4). However, IC₅₀ value of lipid extract obtained by SFE at 90 bar and 40°C, reported by Grosso et al. [27] is two times higher than of our samples. Very high antioxidant property of *S. montana* EO is attributed to high content of carvacrol and the entire group of aromatic oxygenated monoterpenes, which may act as potent radical scavenging agents. Furthermore, according to scientific reference, for same components presented in lower content in *S. montana* EO and extracts, antioxidant activity was confirmed [42]. Vardar-Unlu et al. [43] concluded that possible synergistic or antagonistic effects could be taken into account for constituents of EO, such as α - and γ -terpinene, limonene, *p*-cymene, linalool and others.

Essential oil of *O. basilicum* investigated in this study showed similar antioxidant activity with reported by Hussain et al. [44] and higher than in study of Pripdeevech et al. [45] and Filip et al. [23]. In contrast, Filip et al. [23] reported 6 times higher activity of SF extract obtained at 100 bar and 60°C, than that of our extract (100 bar, 40°C). The difference in antioxidant activity can be explained by difference in content of linalool and eugenol, as two major compounds responsible for antioxidant activity of basil.

C. sativum exhibited the lowest antioxidant activity among investigated plants. The IC₅₀ of EO was slightly better than that report by Singh et al. [46]. However, antioxidant activity of extract was in the range with activity reported by Zeković et al. [39]. Comparing the activity of EO and extract, it could be concluded that SFE extracts exhibited the lowest activity toward DPPH radical, because they

comprise the non-volatile components and other nonpolar compounds such as fatty acids, triglycerides, tocopherols, etc.

Regarding literature data on IC₅₀ values of well-known antioxidant compounds (Table 4) it can be concluded that antioxidant activity of *S. montana* and *O. basilica* EOs is higher than antioxidant activity of Vitamin C, BHT (butylhydroxytoluol) and quercetin. Obtained CO₂ extracts of *S. montana* showed similar antioxidant activity with BHT, confirming the results reported by Vidović et al. [42], which recommend these extracts into a very powerful antioxidants for variety of applications. Also, CO₂ extracts of *O. basilicum* and herbal mixture (CBS sample) can be considered as antioxidants with significant potential for food industry.

3.4. Antiproliferative activity *in vitro*

The results of antiproliferative activity *in vitro* of *S. montana*, *C. sativum*, *O. basilicum* and herbal mixture (CBS sample) are presented in Table 3, and are expressed as IC₅₀ which is amount of a compound (in µg/mL) inhibiting cell survival by 50%. The medicinal plants were tested at three human cancer cell lines: the human cervix adenocarcinoma HeLa cells, human chronic myelogenous leukemia K562 cells and breast cancer MDA-MB-453 cells. Normal fibroblast MRC-5 was used as control cells.

EO and extracts of *S. montana* demonstrated high antiproliferative activity (IC₅₀= 59.85 – 91.05 µg/mL) against HeLa cells line, where the EO is 1.5 times more cytotoxic than CO₂ extracts. A moderate antiproliferative activity, at the same cell lines, exhibited EO and extracts of herbal mixture of *O. basilicum* with IC₅₀ in the range from 173 to 312 µg/mL. In the case of *C. sativum*, only EO can be considered as antiproliferative agent. The antiproliferative activity decrease in following order: EO *S. montana* > extracts *S. montana* > EO CBS > extracts CBS > EO *O. basilicum* > extracts *O. basilicum*. Furthermore, EO and extracts of *S. montana* again demonstrated good antiproliferative activity (IC₅₀= 31–36 µg/mL) against K562 cells line, while EO and extracts of herbal mixture have been shown as a second better result. However, CO₂ CBS extract at low pressure exhibited 3 times less toxic activity than *S. montana* extract obtained at the same SFE conditions. In the case of MDA-MB-453 cells, EO and *S. montana* CO₂ extracts exhibited high antiproliferative activity, compared with other EOs and extracts. In general, EO and CO₂ extracts of *S. montana* exhibited high antiproliferative and anticancer activity with good selectivity in action especially to K562 cells in comparison to normal MRC-5 cells.

Antiproliferative effects of *S. montana* EO and extracts has been shown earlier. According to Četojević-Simin et al. [5] different extracts of *S. montana* exhibited antiproliferative activity on HeLa (human cervix adenocarcinoma), HT-29 (human colon adenocarcinoma) and MCF-7 (human breast adenocarcinoma) cell lines. Cytotoxic activity of *S. montana* EO was recognized by Miladi et al. [40] against A549 (human lung adenocarcinoma) cell line. Koparal & Zeytinoglu [47] demonstrated that carvacrol, the predominant monoterpene in *S. montana*, was very potent cell growth inhibitor of A549 cell line. Research done by Arunasree [48] showed that this type of oil and its major component carvacrol (which constitute 53.35% of the oil) were highly cytotoxic against human metastatic breast cancer cells (MDA-MB 231). Fitiou et al. [49] concluded that carvacrol was the most potent antiproliferative agent against A549 cells, while Hep3B (hepatocellular carcinoma) cells were most sensitive to thymol. Summing up the obtained results, EO and CO₂ extracts of *S. montana* can be consider as potent therapeutic significant in the treatment of cancer.

According to literature data, antiproliferative activity of *O. basilicum* EO and extracts were investigated by Zarlaha et al. [50] *in vitro*, on four different humans cancer cell lines: the human cervix adenocarcinoma HeLa cells, human melanoma FemX cells, human chronic myelogenous leukaemia K562 cells and human ovarian SKOV3 cells. The major constituents of EO and extracts, such as eugenol,

isoeugenol, linalool, caffeic and rosmarinic acid were investigated, too. In this study, isoeugenol, eugenol, linalool and caffeic acid exhibited high cytotoxicity and anticancer activity against human ovarian SKOV3 cells. Comparing our and their results on HeLa and K562 cells, it could be seen that SFE extracts possessed better cytotoxic activity against K562 cells. Cytotoxic activity of *O. basilicum* EO was recognized by Kathirvel & Ravi [51] against HeLa i Hep-2 tumor cells.

Many chemopreventive agents have been developed actively for the prevention and treatment of cancers from medicinal plants, because they usually exert anticarcinogenic activities with fewer side effects than synthesized compounds [52]. This is the main reason while the researches in this field are very actually until today.

3.5. Chemometric analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) were carried out in order to get a better overview of the similarities between essential oil and lipid extracts of *S. montana*, *C. sativum* and *O. basilicum* based on their chemical profile of terpenoid compounds, antioxidant and antiproliferative activity. HCA resulted in two main clusters could be observed in Figure 3. Samples in cluster 1 were divided in two subgroups: one with *C. sativum* extracts obtained by SFE and other with *C. sativum* and *O. basilicum* EOs and *O. basilicum* extract obtained by SFE (OB-SFE1). Samples in cluster were divided in two subgroups as well. *S. montana* EO and extracts obtained by SFE were clearly separated from rest of the samples. Beside CBS EO and lipid extracts, OB-SFE2 was also in the same subgroup, due to similarities in chemical profile (Table 2), which is rather expected since CBS represents the mixture of the investigated plants.

Multivariate statistical approach, i.e. PCA, was applied in order to differentiate EOs and lipid extracts and to possibly correlate terpenoid compounds with antioxidant and antiproliferative activity. Therefore, parameters used for PCA were: content of terpenoid compounds (α -pinene, β -pinene, d-limonene, eucalyptol, γ -terpinene, linalool, camphor, α -terpineol, methyl-chavicol, geraniol, carvacrol and eugenol), antioxidant activity (IC₅₀ towards DPPH radicals) and antiproliferative activity (IC₅₀ towards HeLa, MDA-MB-453, K562 and MRC-5 cell lines). PCA was applied in order to reduce the number of dimensions of the complex system with 17 grouping variables [53]. The first three Principal Components (PC) accounted for 80% of the total variance of the model. It could be observed that the PC1 and PC2 accounted for 68% of the total variance of the model (Figure 4), while PC3 accounted for 23.2% of variance. PC1 was negatively correlated with all grouping parameters except γ -terpinene and carvacrol (Figure 4a). On the other hand, PC2 was positively correlated with content of each terpenoid compound and negatively correlated with IC₅₀ values of antioxidant and antiproliferative activity parameters (Figure 4a).

The distribution of the samples was strongly influence by the type of the plant material since EO and lipid extracts of each plant were grouped together in four subgroups (Coriander, Basil, Winter Savory and CBS) (Figure 4b). *C. sativum* and *S. montana* subgroups were clearly separate, while *O. basilicum* and CBS subgroups exhibited higher deviation from the grouping since they were positioned far from each other on Figure 4b. It could be seen that *O. basilicum* group overlapped with CBS, which is rather expected since CBS EO and lipid extracts were mixtures of these three plants. *S. montana* group is characterized by the high carvacrol content (Figure 4), which is in accordance with data from Table 2. On the other hand, *C. sativum* group was characterized by particularly high IC₅₀ values of antioxidant and antiproliferative activity parameters, suggesting their weak pharmacological activity and good correlation between these parameters. Since IC₅₀ value is reciprocal indicator of antioxidant and antiproliferative activity, it could be expected that higher activity would be typical for groups in opposite quadrant (upper right) (Figure 4). This quadrant is typical for *S. montana* and CBS groups, as

well as carvacrol content which could be designated as the major compound responsible for these actions.

4. Conclusion

Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction, as a “green technology” was employed for extraction aromatic plants: *Satureja montana*, *Coriandrum sativum* and *Ocimum basilicum*, as well as mixture of these three herbs. Chemical profile of EOs and obtained extracts of individual plants, on low pressure (100 bar, 40°C) showed a differences in volatile components. Chemical profile of herbal mixture (CBS) CO₂ extract was completely different than that extracts obtained from individual plants at the same conditions. The most abundant components in the CBS CO₂ extract were carvacrol, linalool, followed by geraniol, γ -terpinene and d-limonene.

Antioxidant activity of obtained CO₂ extracts and isolated EOs were shown that the highest antioxidant activity express *S. montana* and *O. basilicum* EOs. The antioxidant activity of CBS EO was approximately 6 times lower than antioxidant activity of *S. montana* EO, but very similar with extracts of *S. montana* obtained by supercritical extraction procedure (40°C, 100 and 300 bar). Herbal mixture is not exhibited the expected synergistic antioxidant activity, mostly because the coriander extracts possessed the lowest activity toward DPPH radical. However, EO and CO₂ extracts of *S. montana* exhibited high antiproliferative activity against three human cancer cell lines: HeLa, K562 and MDA-MB-453. Synergistic effects of compounds detected in extract (100 bar, 40°C) of three investigated herbs can be consider in case of human chronic myelogenous leukemia K562 cells. Although, the expected better synergistic biological activities are absent, further research is still required with other combinations of herbal mixture of three investigated herbs.

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Figure Captions

Fig. 1. Extraction kinetics of *S. montana*, *C. sativum*, *O. basilicum* and CBS (herbal mixture).

Fig. 2. Compounds content in obtained essential oils and extracts.

Fig. 3. Dendrogram obtained by HCA based on complete linkage algorithm and Euclidean distance

Fig. 4. a) Bi-plot distribution and b) score plot of PC1 and PC2 for grouping of EOs and extracts

Figures

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Tables

Table 1. Raw material characterization, content of essential oil (EOs) and extraction yield obtained by SFE

Sample	Raw material characterization		Yield (%)		
	d_p (mm) ^b	Moisture (%)	EO	100 bar, 40°C	300 bar, 40°C
<i>S. montana</i>	0.377	9.68	1.15	1.50	4.02
<i>C. sativum</i>	0.562	7.31	0.75	1.74	5.60
<i>O. basilicum</i>	0.307	8.45	0.67	1.56	2.07
CBS ^a	0.415	8.48	0.78	2.00	4.29

^a CBS – herbal mixture (*S. montana* + *C. sativum* + *O. basilicum*)

^b Mean particle diameter (d_p)

Table 2. Chemical composition of *S. montana*, *C. sativum*, *O. basilicum* and herbal mixture (CBS) essential oils and CO₂ extracts identified by GC-MS (GC-FID)

Component	Content (mg/g extract)															
	<i>Satureja montana</i>				<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>				<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>				CBS			
	EO	SFE			EO	SFE			EO	SFE			EO	SFE		
	100	bar,	300	bar,	100	bar,	300	bar,	100	bar,	300	bar,	100	bar,	300	bar,
	40°C		40°C		40°C		40°C		40°C		40°C		40°C		40°C	
α -Pinene	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		1.00	<0.1	<0.1		4.40	<0.1	6.50		5.10	5.30	1.80	
β -Pinene	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		<0.1	<0.1	4.80		3.60	3.60	1.00	
d-Limonene	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		2.90	1.00	4.10		3.70	10.40	2.00	
Eucalyptol	3.10	0.90	<0.1		<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		32.10	<0.1	12.10		11.60	3.20	2.10	
γ -Terpinene	52.20	<0.1	4.30		<0.1	<0.1	1.20		<0.1	<0.1	12.00		18.60	42.00	2.00	
Linalool	8.10	32.00	2.80		782.0	456.00	291.20		0	301.00	379.00		0	101.00	102.00	
Camphor	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		11.00	3.30	8.20		7.50	5.60	17.10		9.90	4.20	2.10	
α -Terpineol	1.20	<0.1	0.80		4.20	<0.1	<0.1		8.70	4.10	17.00		5.20	5.10	1.00	
Methyl-chavicol	2.00	<0.1	<0.1		1.00	<0.1	11.20		21.00	8.20	6.10		7.60	5.20	1.20	
Geraniol	2.10	<0.1	<0.1		1.20	<0.1	<0.1		22.00	7.10	9.10		29.00	61.00	2.20	
Carvacrol	0	529.70	601.70		<0.1	<0.1	2.10		5.20	6.20	12.00		0	281.00	12.00	
Eugenol	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		<0.1	<0.1	<0.1		39.60	<0.1	4.00		15.30	<0.1	1.10	
Monoterpene hydrocarbons	52.20	<0.1	4.30		1.00	<0.1	1.20		7.30	1.00	27.40		31.00	61.30	6.80	
Oxygenated monoterpenes	14.50	32.90	3.60		798.4	459.30	299.40		0	317.80	434.30		0	174.50	109.40	
Aromatic oxygenated monoterpenes	573.0												194.9			
	0	529.70	601.70		1.00	<0.1	13.30		65.80	14.40	22.10		0	286.20	14.30	
	639.7				800.4				915.4				703.6			
Total	0	562.60	609.60		0	459.30	313.90		0	333.20	483.80		0	522.00	130.50	

Table 3. Antioxidant and antiproliferative activity of EOs and extracts

Sample	Extracion conditions		DPPH IC ₅₀ [µg/mL]	IC ₅₀ [µg/mL]			
				HeLa	K562	MDA-MB-453	MRC-5
<i>S. montana</i>	EO		5.05 ± 1.52	59.85 ± 8.55	35.70 ± 1.40	94.40 ± 6.70	81.25 ± 0.85
	SFE (100 bar, 40°)		27.43 ± 3.48	88.25 ± 10.85	31.70 ± 2.50	154.60 ± 13.90	109.90 ± 11.20
	SFE (300 bar, 40°)		28.71 ± 2.41	91.05 ± 3.85	35.80 ± 1.80	113.30 ± 7.60	152.30 ± 10.50
<i>C. sativum</i>	EO		39.12 ± 3.39	292.85 ± 7.25	387.20 ± 57.20	697.40 ± 20.20	751.00 ± 6.00
	SFE (100 bar, 40°)		5.27 10 ³ ± 0.25	647.50 ± 85.00	188.85 ± 2.15	777.70 ± 23.60	752.00 ± 58.60
	SFE (300 bar, 40°)		6.78 10 ³ ± 0.31	751.60 ± 70.90	189.25 ± 7.35	925.20 ± 55.60	972.00 ± 26.00
<i>O. basilicum</i>	EO		6.94 ± 1.27	285.70 ± 13.20	220.00 ± 2.50	536.50 ± 13.80	719.70 ± 9.10
	SFE (100 bar, 40°)		118.52 ± 4.74	312.85 ± 18.85	145.50 ± 10.70	610.60 ± 28.50	744.85 ± 35.25
	SFE (300 bar, 40°)		182.03 ± 6.98	223.45 ± 18.75	116.50 ± 3.70	386.95 ± 39.65	409.30 ± 40.40
CBS	EO		28.24 ± 2.17	173.80 ± 8.90	117.55 ± 2.85	254.05 ± 30.25	351.40 ± 13.60
	SFE (100 bar, 40°)		104.90 ± 3.91	228.60 ± 1.40	92.10 ± 0.50	386.35 ± 29.55	383.20 ± 1.00
	SFE (300 bar, 40°)		228.35 ± 6.72	267.00 ± 13.90	112.65 ± 2.05	440.10 ± 40.10	484.05 ± 4.65

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation

Table 4. Antioxidant activity of EOs and extracts from previous study and of well known antioxidants

Samples	IC₅₀ (µg/mL)	References
<i>Satureja montana</i>		
EO	5,490 ± 260	[31]
EO	508.45	[30]
EO	410.5 ± 4.27	[40]
EO	243.80 ± 4.93	[41]
SFE (90 bar, 40°C)	60.00 ± 0.00	[27]
<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>		
EO	47.2	[46]
SFE (100 bar, 40 °C)	5269.00	[39]
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>		
EO	4.8 – 6.7	[44]
EO	26.53	[45]
EO	52.92 ± 0.01	[23]
SFE (100 bar, 60 °C)	18.93 ± 0.02	[23]
Antioxidants		
Quarctetin	10.5	[55]
Vitamin C	16	[54]
BHT	24	[54]